

Original article

Pattern and uptake of pap smear at federal university of health sciences teaching hospital Azare, north-east, Nigeria: a retrospective study

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Abstract

Background: Cervical cancer is the second most common cancer among women aged 15 to 44 years. An effective screening measure ensures early detection of premalignant lesions, prompt treatment and prevention of cervical cancer. Pap smear screenings have been associated with a 60% reduction in cervical cancer rates for women over the age of 40 years. However, the uptake of cervical cancer screening has been uncoordinated, erratic, and mostly opportunistic in low-resource countries like Nigeria. This is more so in the Northeastern part of the country, where the healthcare system has been disrupted by years of insurgency. The study was conducted to determine the post-insurgency pattern and uptake of Pap smear in FUHSTHA, Bauchi, Northeast Nigeria. **Materials and methods:** A hospital-based retrospective cross-sectional study was conducted among 77 women who attended the reproductive health clinic of the Obstetrics and Gynaecology department from January 2020 to December 2022. A total number of 4,458 patients/clients attended RHC during the period, and 1,364 (79.2%) of the folders were retrieved and reviewed. Only 77 clients who had Pap smears and had their results documented were included in the study. **Results:** The study revealed a Pap smear uptake of 2.1%, with uptake over the 3-year period almost double that of the preceding year. The prevalence of pre-invasive cervical lesions was 9.1%, of which AGCUS was 1.3%, ASCUS 3.9%, LGSIL 2.6% and HGSIL 1.3%. Most of the clients were referred (82%), and 41.6% of the women were between 50 – 59 years. Indication for the test was routine screening 51.9%, vaginal bleeding 29.9%, and persistent vaginal discharge 18.2%. The majority (96.1%) were immune-competent, while 3.9% were immune-compromised at presentation. The predictors independently associated with abnormal cytology were lack of formal education (AOR = 3.60; 95% CI: 1.14–11.38; p = 0.029); early age (< 19 years) at first marriage (AOR = 4.23; 95% CI: 1.30–13.78; p = 0.017); and early age (< 20 years) at first pregnancy (AOR = 3.10; 95% CI: 1.03–9.34; p = 0.044). **Conclusion:** Pap smear uptake was low with significant pre-invasive cervical lesions. Strengthening awareness, integrating screening into routine care, improving access to screening, and implementing supportive policies are essential to increase Pap smear uptake and reduce the burden of cervical cancer.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, Screening, Pap smear, Cytology

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20669915>

Date Submitted: 9th May 2026

Date Accepted: 2nd June 2026

Date Published Online: 12th June 2026

Cite this article as: Achanya E. Sunday,* Olayinka T. Hassan, Agbogo Emmanuel, Abubakar D. Katagum, Abdullahi A. Habib, Uchenna Ezenkwa, Zakka Musa, Issa S. Aboubacar, Anigbogu Christopher, Ado D. Geidam, Bala M. Audu. Pattern and Uptake of Pap Smear at Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare, North-East, Nigeria: a Retrospective Study. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; 2 (1): 304-312.

Introduction

Cervical cancer, though a preventable disease and a major reproductive health problem, is an important contributor to the global cancer burden and a significant cause of mortality.¹ Low- and middle-income countries, including Nigeria, have been experiencing an epidemiological transition in disease burden from infectious to non-communicable diseases like cancer, more so in women. In 2022, there were approximately 660,000 new cases and 350,000 deaths, with 94% of these deaths occurring in Low- and middle-income countries.² The 5-year survival rate for the patients diagnosed when the cancer is localised is 91% and

falls to 57% for the last presentation with regional and distant stage diseases, respectively.³

An incidence of 42 per 100,000 per year has been reported in Saharan Africa, approximately four times that of high-income countries.⁴ In Nigeria, 12,075 new cases and 7,968 deaths from cervical cancer occur annually.⁵ Cervical cancer remained the predominant gynaecological cancer in women in Northern Nigeria^{5,6} and important aetiological factors contributing to cervical cancer in these women include early marriages, early age of initiating coitus, low socio-economic status and grand multiparity.⁵

The global strategy for cervical cancer elimination by the World Health Organisation as a public health problem includes HPV vaccination, screening and treatment of premalignant and malignant cervical diseases.

Pap smear is an effective evidence-based screening tool that assesses the cervix and ensures early detection of premalignant lesions, giving the opportunity for prompt and effective treatment before the emergence of the invasive disease.⁷⁻⁹ This has invariably helped in reducing rates of incident invasive cervical cancer and cervical cancer death in HPV exposed women. Despite the availability of these strategies, the uptake of cervical cancer, especially in northeastern Nigeria, has been uncoordinated, erratic, and mostly opportunistic due to healthcare system disruption by years of insurgency, fragmented governance, and inconsistent policy implementation. This can be a contributing factor to increased cancer-related morbidity and mortality.¹⁰⁻¹² Factors that impact the uptake of cervical cancer screening can be categorised into individual, community, and systemic levels.¹³⁻¹⁶ There is limited data available on the effect of insurgency on the health status of women and the impact on the cervical cancer screening programme.

Therefore, this study aims to determine the uptake of Pap smear as a means of cervical cancer screening at Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare (FUHSTHA), Bauchi State, Northeast Nigeria. This will help in planning and priority setting for disease prevention and management among underserved populations in the region, a key to reducing cervical cancer incidence.

Since 1988, the Bethesda System for Reporting Cervical Cytology has been the accepted reporting system in the United States. The 2014 revision is the most recent.¹⁷ The reporting format considers Specimen type, Specimen adequacy, General Categorisation, Interpretation/Result, Epithelial

Cell Abnormalities and other malignant neoplasms.^{18,19}

Materials and methods

Study design

The study was a retrospective study of women who had Pap smear for cervical cancer screening at the reproductive health clinic (RHC) in the department of obstetrics and gynaecology of FUHSTHA, Bauchi State, from January 2020 to December 2022.

Study population

Women/clients who attended the RHC of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, had an indication for screening, were referred for a Pap smear, or were undergoing routine screening were included in the study. While women who have undergone a Pap smear test within the period and the result is missing or not documented, pregnant women, those who were menstruating, and those who were already diagnosed with cervical cancer were excluded from the study.

Data collection

The sociodemographic factors and reproductive history of these patients were extracted from their folders, retrieved from the RHC's record unit. A total of 77 folders of patients that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were retrieved and analysed.

Ethical approval

The study was approved by the Institutional Research and Ethics Committee of FUHSTHA, Bauchi State with reference number FMCA/COM/35/VOL,1.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive indices, including means and standard deviations for quantitative variables and counts and percentages for categorical variables, were reported. Predictors of abnormal cytology were analysed using multivariate logistic regression. Results were reported in prose, tables and graphs. Analysis was performed using SPSS version 24.0. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Over the 3-year study period from January 2020 to December 2022, a total of 4,458 patients attended the gynaecological and reproductive health clinic of FUHSTHA, of whom 92 had a Pap smear, giving a Pap smear uptake of 2.1%. However, only 85 folders of these patients were retrieved, giving a retrieval rate of 92.4%. There were 8 folders with either incomplete patient information or no documented Pap smear result, which were excluded from the final analysis. Therefore, 77 patients' folders were analysed in this study. **Sociodemographic characteristics of patients**

The mean age of the patients was 47.52 ± 9.63 years. About 41.6% of the patients were between 50 and 59 years, and 62.3% were of the Hausa/Fulani ethnic group. Other sociodemographic characteristics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of patients

Socio-demographics	Freq (f)	Per cent (%)
Age (years)		
20 – 29	3	3.9
30 – 39	13	16.8
40 – 49	24	31.2
50 – 59	32	41.6
≥60	5	6.5
Ethnicity		
Hausa/Fulani	48	62.3
Yoruba	10	13.0
Igbo	4	5.2
Others	15	19.5
Religion		
Christianity	20	26.0
Islam	57	74.0
Education		
None	5	6.5
Quranic	43	55.8
Primary	11	14.3
Secondary	10	13.0
Tertiary	8	10.4
Occupation		
Unemployed	59	76.6
Informal employment	13	16.9
Formal employment	5	6.5
Parity		
Nulliparity	2	2.6
Multiparity	54	70.1
Grandmultiparity	21	27.3
Age at first marriage (years)		
< 19	37	48.0
20 - 24	25	32.5
≥ 25	15	19.5
Age at first pregnancy (years)		
< 20	48	62.3
21 - 24	25	32.5
≥ 25	4	5.2

Informal employment: Included artisans, petty traders

Pap smear characteristics of patients

Eighty two percent (82%) of women were referred for Pap smear screening. About 51.9% of clients had no symptoms, as they presented only for their routine Pap smear. About 96.1% of the patients were immune-competent. The present study included 77 Pap smear results, of which 68 (88.3%) were normal (table 2). The prevalence of abnormal cytology was 9.1%.

Table 2: Pap smear characteristics of patients

Variables	Frequen cy (f)	Percent (%)
Presentation for pap smear		
Referred	63	82.0
Not referred	14	18.0
Indication for pap smear		
Routine screening	40	51.9
Vaginal bleeding	23	29.9
Persistent Vaginal discharge	14	18.2
Immune status		
Competent	74	96.1
Compromised	3	3.9
Cytology reports		
Normal	67	87.0
Inflammatory	3	3.9
AGCUS	1	1.3
ASCUS	3	3.9
LGSIL	2	2.6
HGSIL	1	1.3

Figure 1: Trend of Pap smear uptake from 2020 to 2022

AGCUS: Atypical Glandular Cells of Undetermined Significance, ASCUS: Atypical Squamous Cells of Undetermined Significance, LGSIL: Low-Grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion, HGSIL: High-Grade Squamous Intraepithelial Lesion.

The uptake of Pap smear over the 3-year period seems to almost double the preceding year, as depicted by the progressive increase in the number of clients screened from 11 in 2020 to 25 in 2021 and then 41 in 2022.

Predictors of abnormal cytology

The predictors independently associated with abnormal cytology were lack of formal education (AOR = 3.60; 95% CI: 1.14–11.38; p = 0.029); early age (< 19 years) at first marriage (AOR = 4.23; 95% CI: 1.30–13.78; p = 0.017); and early age (< 20 years) at first pregnancy (AOR = 3.10; 95% CI: 1.03–9.34; p = 0.044). (Table 3).

Table 3: Multivariate logistic regression predicting abnormal cervical cytology

Variable	AOR	95% CI	p-value
Age (years)			
< 50	1		
≥50	2.03	0.57 – 7.21	0.271
Education			
Formal education	1		
No formal education	3.60	1.14 – 11.38	0.029
Employment			
Employed	1		
Unemployed	1.79	0.52 – 6.12	0.347
Parity			
Multiparity	1		
Grandmultiparity	2.75	0.89 – 8.49	0.078
Age at first marriage (years)			
≥ 19	1		
< 19	4.23	1.30 – 13.78	0.017
Age at first pregnancy (years)			
≥ 20	1		
< 20	3.10	1.03 – 9.34	0.044
Presentation for pap smear			
Referred	1		
Not referred	2.89	0.80 – 10.39	0.102

AOR: adjusted odds ratio, CI: confidence interval

Discussion

Cervical cancer, despite being a preventable disease by appropriate screening modalities like Pap smear, showed an abysmally low level of uptake (2.1%) in this study. Furthermore, the study demonstrated clearly that independent predictors for abnormal cytology were lack of education, age at first marriage and age of first sexual intercourse.

This low level of Pap smear uptake has been reported from other parts of the country. It was 6.49% in Ogun,²⁰ 6.5% in Lagos,²¹ 8% in Ilorin²² and 9% found in Ibadan.²³ This was, however, higher than the less than 1% found among women in a slum community in another study in Lagos.²⁴

The same pattern of low uptake was observed in other African countries. Pap smear prevalence rates were 7% in Ghana, Côte d’Ivoire and Tanzania, respectively.^{25,26,27} However, it was found to be 17% and 25.6% in studies conducted in Kenya.^{28,29} This was higher than the value obtained in our study and may be due to the larger sample size and socio-demographic differences between the populations studied. A study among women attending a tertiary care hospital in Delhi, India, found 7.3% uptake of Pap smear.³⁰

Contrasting patterns have been reported across developed countries worldwide. Pap smear screening uptake among immigrant women in Ontario, Canada, was 53.1%, and 79% in Texas, respectively.^{31,32} This may not be unrelated to the

well-established, coordinated, routine cervical cancer screening programmes in these countries.

The prevalence of pre-invasive cervical lesion (abnormal cytology) from the Pap smear results analysis was 9.1%. This was consistent with 9.8%, 10.8% and 11.8% in Kano, Enugu and Ibadan respectively.^{5,6,33} It was higher than what was obtained in Lagos 4.1³⁴ and Ibadan 7.1%.³⁵ This may be due to the fact that early marriage and early age at first childbearing,²³ both been aetiological factors for dysplasia/carcinoma of the cervix are very common in Northern Nigeria as the case in this study. However, it was less than 26.4 % found among women in India.³⁶

The mean age of the women in this study was 47.52 ± 9.63 years which fall within the recommended age for cervical cancer screening³⁷. This finding contrasted that from Lagos and Sokoto among women attending reproductive health clinic where the with mean age at Pap smear screening was 37.7% ± 9.5 years and 32.8 ± 9.3 years respectively.^{38,39} This may be explained by differences in the population studied, sample size and the study design. This findings is also higher than the median age of Pap smear uptake of 37.20 ± 9.1 years reported among Iranian women. Despite the fact that these women have similar socio-demographic and reproductive characteristic with those of our study.⁴⁰ However, the difference of more than a decade may be connected to the large sample size of 440 and the cross sectional census methodology employed.

Almost half of the women were less than 19 years at first marriage. This was corroborated by a study among women in Indonesia where age at marriage of less than 20 year was associated with cervical dysplasia and cancer.⁴¹

A study among Iraqi women also found out that a quarter (28%) of the women at age 15 – 18 year at their first marriage while a third (60.2%) of them were greater than 18 years at first delivery, thereby predisposing them to abnormal cervical changes later in life.^{18,42} This is very significant as early age at first marriage invariably lead to early sexual debut, and with the increased risk associated with persistent HPV infection and the biological predisposition of the immature cervix during adolescent result in greater chance of cervical dysplasia and cancer development. This is most likely so because marriage at early age may lead to limited education, economic disadvantages, reliance on spouses for healthcare financing, and socio-cultural norms that prioritize childbearing over preventive healthcare services. Therefore, they are less likely to benefit from HPV vaccination, and

regular cervical cancer screening. Consequently, there is need for strategic stakeholders or community engagement/advocacy and legislative procedure to drive policy change that will delay age at first marriage and interventions tailored to these vulnerable population.

Furthermore, the present study clearly revealed that women who had no form of education were least likely to be involved in cervical cancer screening. This is likely because educated women due to better health enlightenment generally have good health seeking behavior and consequently more likely to undertake cervical cancer screening. This was consistent with similar findings from studies done by ACCP in South Africa, Kenya, India and Peru, on factors influencing Pap smear uptake.⁴³ It was also supported by study conducted in resource-limited countries that identified educational level, and employment have a significant impact on uptake of Pap smear for cervical cancer screening.⁴⁴ It has also been reported in other low income countries that rural women with no education are less likely to be involved in cervical cancer screening as compared to younger, more educated women in the cities.^{45,46} These category of women even though small (6.5%) form a larger pool of the population and need to be informed on the burden, risk factor, prevention (through HPV vaccination and screening) and treatment of cervical cancer in line with global objectives.

This study also revealed high rate of compliance with Pap smear for cervical cancer screening among multi- and grand-multiparous women indicating that frequent contact with health care facility/provider during antenatal and postnatal care increases awareness and uptake of cervical cancer screening. This was supported by similar findings from studies conducted in India.^{46,47} However, some other studies have reported less compliance with cervical cancer screening with higher number of pregnancies.⁴⁸

The pattern of cytology in our study found that majority (87%) of the women had normal cytology, 3.9% inflammatory cells and 9.1% abnormal cytology. Interestingly, a similar pattern was observed in a study in Kano, Northwest and Kogi, North central Nigeria respectively.^{49,50} However, finding from a study in Maiduguri Northeast region showed a different pattern of 36.3%, 40.3% normal and inflammatory cytology respectively.⁵¹ This variation may be due to prevalence of sexually transmitted infection and magnitude of multiple sexual partners in the area.

Our study revealed a very low level of Pap smear uptake for cervical cancer screening despite the

high volume of clinic attendance by sexually active women at risk of cervical cancer. This showcases the need for strategic awareness campaigns on cervical cancer, the risk factors, necessity of regular screening and improved access to services.

Strength and limitation of the study

While the findings of this research offer valuable insights into the uptake and pattern of Pap smear at FUHSTH Azare, Bauchi Northeast Nigeria, it is imperative to acknowledge the limitations inherent in the study design. The retrospective design of the study relies on secondary data sources, from health records and folders, which are subject to retrieval challenges, inaccuracies, missing data, or incomplete documentation. Also, the relatively small size of the sample analyzed may not have been adequately powered to make far-reaching generalizable conclusion. Therefore, prospective, multi-centre study will be of paramount importance to elucidate prevalence, pattern of Pap smear uptake and strongest independent determinant of abnormal cytology in the Northeastern region of Nigeria.

Conclusion

Pap smear uptake was extremely low despite significant pre-invasive lesions, indicating missed prevention opportunities. Education, early marriage and early age at first pregnancy, and access influenced cervical cancer screening and abnormal cytology. Therefore, strengthening awareness, integrating screening into routine care, promoting vaccination for HPV, improving access to screening, empowering women through education, and implementing supportive policies are essential to increase pap smear uptake and reduce burden of the cancer of the cervix.

Conflict of interest:

None.

Funding:

No external funding was received.

Data availability:

Data is available on reasonable request.

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